

THE INFLUENCE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE LITERATURE ON UZBEK LITERATURE

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Annotation: This article explores the influence of English language literature on Uzbek literature.

Keywords: English literature, Uzbek literature, influence, analysis

В данной статье рассматривается влияние английской литературы на узбекскую литературу.

Английская литература, узбекская литература, влияние, анализ

Uzbek literature is not an exception to the strong influence that English literature has had on literary traditions around the world. A vast interchange of concepts, themes, and literary devices characterizes the complex and dynamic interaction between Uzbek and English language literature. In order to enrich and broaden Uzbek literature, this article will examine the numerous ways that English language literature has influenced Uzbek literature.

The incorporation of narrative techniques and structural features is one clear way that English language writing has influenced Uzbek literature. English novels and short tales have served as a frequent source of inspiration for Uzbek authors, who have incorporated plot development, character characterization, and narrative voice into their own works. By studying the works of renowned English authors, Uzbek writers have expanded their repertoire of literary techniques, enhancing the depth and complexity of Uzbek literature.

Furthermore, there is a noticeable thematic effect of English-language literature on Uzbek literature. Love, grief, identity, and societal difficulties are just

a few of the subjects that English literature tackles and which both Uzbek writers and readers find meaningful. Uzbek writers' works resonate with themes of social justice, cultural identity, and the human condition as they represent the universality of human experiences and are portrayed in English literature.

Additionally, the dissemination of English literary concepts and viewpoints inside Uzbek literary circles has been made easier by the translation of literary works from English into Uzbek. By acting as cultural bridges, translations give readers in Uzbekistan access to the diverse canon of English literature. Uzbek authors interact with many literary traditions through translations, promoting intercultural communication and understanding.

To conclude, the impact of English-language literature on Uzbek literature demonstrates the interdependence of worldwide literary customs. The creative, innovative, and culturally exchange-promoting interchange of ideas, themes, and literary devices between English and Uzbek literature enhances the cultural fabric of both literary traditions. Undoubtedly, Uzbek literature's interaction with English-language literature will remain a crucial component of its ongoing evolution.

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